

Analysis of Trade Characteristics and Potential between China and North African Countries Based on Gravity Model

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Abstract: The term "NAF" is used to denote a group of North African countries that are considered emerging economies. These countries include Algeria, Tunisia, Morocco, West Sahara, Mauritania, Libya, Sudan, South Sudan, and Egypt. The gross domestic product (GDP) of the country surpasses that of established European nations. Simultaneously, these nine nations possess a substantial population, rendering them the contemporary and preeminent entity in the intricate and perpetually evolving global landscape. This study utilizes comprehensive data on China's import and export trade spanning the years 2004 to 2022 to elucidate the correlation between China's import and export trade and the member countries of North Africa. The analysis encompasses multiple dimensions, including an overview of trade development, trade balance, and the structure of traded commodities. This study also conducts a qualitative analysis of the potential of China's import and export trade with the member countries of North Africa, utilizing data on the trade volume and GDP of the selected countries.

Keywords: China; North African countries; Trade potential; Gravitational model

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Introduction

The North African countries "NAF" refers to emerging economies composed of, Algeria, Tunisia, Morocco, West Sahara, Mauritan, Libya, Sudan, South Sudan and Egypt. As a new multilateral cooperation mechanism and economic governance platform, the emergence and development of the North African countries have become the latest emerging major force in the international situation. At the same time as the North African countries are developing rapidly, it corresponds to the complex and ever-changing international economic situation. On the one hand, trade protectionism is constantly rising, and anti-globalization is becoming a common trend, threatening the smooth progress of trade liberalization and globalization. On the other hand, world trade has entered the era of digital economy, ushering in a new era of digitalization. Under a series of severe and full of development opportunities, these nine countries have a large population and GDP far exceeding that of the old developed countries in Europe, with a huge international

influence; At the same time, China adheres to the concept of open and inclusive economic development, actively promotes economic and trade exchanges between North African countries, and has made the strongest promotion and best demonstration for the development of global economy, trade cooperation, and economic globalization.

In summary, it can be concluded that each of the nine countries has its own development limitations and potential for further improvement. Therefore, China. Seeking cooperation and mutual benefit with the four countries is an inevitable requirement for the North African countries to pursue long-term stability and rapid development. In this context, studying the import and export trade relations between China and other North African countries is of great practical significance for China to implement trade diversification, expand trade space, increase its ability to resist external shocks, and achieve sustainable development of its own economy. Sheng Bin et al. (2009) used a gravity model to examine the determinants of export trade flows in emerging market economies, and estimated China's export potential with 40 major trading partner countries in terms of both total volume and sector; Joseph Pearson, Wilma, Ludo et al, Analyzed the flow and potential of China's bilateral service trade: Li Yabo (2018) used import and export data from bilateral meetings between China and Chile from 1992 to 2016 to describe the development status of bilateral trade and calculated the potential of China Chile bilateral trade using a gravity model; Zheng Xuedang and Zhuang Rui (2020) used relevant data from 2005 to 201 to construct a modified Constant Market Share Model (CMS) to study the growth factors of China's exports to other NAF countries. The market demand induced effect and export price competition effect have always been the main factors for China's export growth to other NAF countries, and the mismatch between export supply and import demand leads to lower export structure effects. The expansion of market demand in Morocco and Tunisia has led to a sustained increase in the contribution of market demand induced effects to export growth; The growth of exports to Algeria has undergone a transition from export price competition to market demand induced effects; Yuan Qigang and Wang Yue et al. (2020) conducted a study on the export price competition effect in Egypt at the bilateral level. They first analyzed the factors that affect the export trade potential at the aggregate level and estimated the potential difference between the two countries. Finally, based on this potential difference, they analyzed the export trade potential at the industry level, which is also a way to refine and deepen the analysis of trade potential. This article will also study the trade potential between China and the NAF member countries based on the trade gravity model.

2. Methodology

2.1 Construction of Gravity Model

The gravitational model is derived from the "law of gravity" and originated from the universal gravity formula of Newton's classical mechanics in physics. Later, Tinbergen et al. (1962) extended it in the field of economics and proposed a relatively complete and computationally convenient economic model - the gravitational model. The main meaning is that the trade flow between two economies is directly proportional to their respective economic scale (usually expressed in GDP) and inversely proportional to the spatial distance between economies. It is currently a basic and commonly used tool in the international trade theory community to study and predict international trade flow. This article is based on previous scholars' research on the gravity model of trade, and based on the actual situation of China's import and export trade, attempts to establish a gravity model of China's impact on the import and export trade of the other four NAF countries, and evaluate the potential of trade. In trade theory, the gravitational equation usually adopts the product form:

$$T_{ij} = \alpha_0 Y_i^{\beta_1} Y_j^{\beta_2} \text{Dist}_{ij}^{\beta_3} \eta$$

The natural logarithmic form of the trade gravity model is generally expressed as follows:

$$\ln T_{ij} = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln Y_i + \beta_2 \ln Y_j + \beta_3 \ln \text{Dist}_{ij} + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Among them, $\alpha = \ln \alpha_0$ (α_0 is commonly referred to as the gravitational coefficient) $\varepsilon = \ln \eta$ (random error term). T_{ij} is the trade flow between the i and j countries, Y_j and Y_i are the gross domestic product (GDP) of the i -th and j -th countries, respectively. Dist_{ij} represents the spatial distance between the i -th and j -th countries (generally referring to the distance between the capitals of two countries). The basic meaning of this equation is that the bilateral

trade volume between the two trading parties is positively correlated with their domestic economic aggregate, and inversely proportional to the trade distance between the two countries. Factors such as borders and population are included in the residual term. The coefficients β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 reflect the elasticity of T_n towards Y_i , Y_j , and $Dist_n$. When the i -th country's GDP increases by 1%, the bilateral trade volume between the two countries increases by $\beta_1\%$. When the j th country's GDP increases by 1%, the bilateral trade volume between the two countries increases by $\beta_2\%$. When the distance between the j th country increases by 1%, the bilateral trade volume between the two countries increases by $\beta_3\%$.

According to the research purpose of this article, based on model (1), to establish a gravity model suitable for analyzing the potential of China's import and export trade with North African countries (Naf), this article introduces new explanatory variables, such as the population of the trading country, whether it is an African Union (AU) member state, and whether it borders. Considering that China often exhibits significant differences in import and export in its foreign trade, if import and export are not distinguished, However, only examining the total trade volume is not scientific for analyzing China's trade potential. Therefore, this article transforms the classic trade gravity model into two gravity models: import and export trade.

Specifically, the linearized import trade gravity model is:

$$\ln I_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln Y_1 + \beta_2 \ln Y_{it} + \beta_3 \ln Dist_i + \beta_4 Naf + \beta_5 AU + \beta_6 Adj_1 + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Among them, $i = 1, \dots, 30, t = 2018, \dots, 2022$, α represents a constant term, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$, and β_6 represent regression coefficients, and ε represents a random error term.

The linearized export trade model is:

$$\ln E_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln Y_1 + \beta_2 \ln Y_{it} + \beta_3 \ln Dist_i + \beta_4 Naf + \beta_5 AU + \beta_6 Adj_1 + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

Among them, $i = 1, \dots, 30, t = 2018, \dots, 2022$, α is a constant term, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$, and β_6 are regression coefficients, and ε is a random error term.

2.2 Variable Selection

Due to the large number of countries involved in constructing the trade gravity equation and considering the availability of data, the regression sample selected by the author is the top 30 countries or regions in terms of bilateral trade volume with China in 2022. Although not all countries or regions can be selected, the total trade volume between China and these 30 countries or regions accounts for over 80% of the total foreign trade volume. The sample has strong representativeness and basically reflects China's foreign trade situation. At the same time, regarding other important variables in this model, such as trade distance and whether the border samples cover countries and regions from various continents around the world, the distances between them have significant differences and can meet the requirements of the model. Therefore, the import and export trade data between Sichuan China and these countries or regions are more comprehensive, and the import and export trade potential of China's trade with the NAF countries is also more convincing.

According to the ranking of the total import and export volume of customs between China and other countries (regions) in the 2018 Statistical Yearbook of China, we selected the United States, Japan, Germany, Australia, the United Kingdom, Pakistan, Tunisia, Egypt, Morocco, Hong Kong, Angola, Canada, Chile, France, Indonesia, Iran, Italy, Kazakhstan, South Korea, Malaysia, Mexico, the Netherlands, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, Switzerland, the United Arab Emirates of Thailand Vietnam, Taiwan, China, China and other 30 countries or regions as research objects This paper collected 19 years of panel data from 2004 to 2022 in the above countries, with 570 valid samples. Due to non endogenous reasons, the UN COMTRADE database did not include import and export data from Central and South China in 2004. This data is obtained from the 2005 China Statistical Yearbook, which lists the total import and export volume of customs between China and other countries (regions). The selected data structure is balanced short panel data, which can effectively avoid the randomness of cross-sectional data and deepen the sampling accuracy of the estimator. At the same time, examining

the differences in imports and exports between the two countries from both individual and temporal perspectives can enhance the unbiased and effective sample regression.

Please refer to Table 1 for the expected symbols and model data sources regarding the meaning of the explanatory and dependent variables. The model and data processing in this article were carried out using Eviews6.0 software.

Table 1 Variable description and data Source

Variable	Concept	Database
$\ln E_{it}$	The logarithm of China's exports to country i in year t	UN COMTRADE database
$\ln I_{it}$	The logarithm of China's imports from country i in year t	UN COMTRADE database
$\ln P_{it}$	The logarithm of population 1 in year t in country i	World Bank WDI data
$\ln Y_{it}$	The logarithm of GDP of country i in year t	World Bank WDI data
$\ln Dist_i$	The logarithmic distance between China and country i uses the geography between the two capitals	CEPII data array
NAF	The lake pseudo variable, if both countries are from the same family, is 1, and the opposite is 0	CEPII data array
AU	Quasi variable, if both are AFRICAN UNION (AU) members, it is 1, and on the contrary, it is 0	CEPII data array
Adj_j	Quasi variable, it has a connected boundary, if there is one, it will be taken as 1, and if not, it will be taken as 0	CEPI1 database

3. Analysis of Inspection Results

Panel data is generally divided into three categories: mixed effects models, random effects models, and fixed effects models. In a mixed model, the intercept and slope terms are the same for any individual and cross-section, and there is no need to distinguish between them. The mixed least squares method is directly used to estimate the parameters. In both fixed and random models, the estimation results of the equation should be different for different individuals and cross-sections in terms of intercept or slope. Therefore, a variable intercept model or a variable coefficient equation can be chosen for regression. The main difference between random and fixed effects models is that in the random effects model, the error term is not related to the explanatory variable, while in the fixed effects model, the random error term is related to the explanatory variable. The advantage of a random effects model is that it saves freedom. If the data has significant changes in both time series and cross-section, then choosing a random effects model can clearly describe the characteristics of the error source. The advantage of the fixed effects model is that it is easy to analyze the degree of difference between the mean of the dependent variable corresponding to any cross-sectional data and the mean of the dependent variable corresponding to all cross-sectional data. The national effect model does not require the individual effect components in the error term to be uncorrelated with the explanatory variables in the model. It should be noted that when this assumption is not established, it may cause inconsistency in the estimation of model parameters.

3.1 Empirical testing of the import trade gravity model

From the empirical results of the import trade model between China and 30 countries (Table 2) firstly, from the F-statistic and accompanying probability values of the three models, the three regression equations are significant. However, in terms of adjusting the R-value, the fixed effects model has the best fitting degree, with a model interpretation degree of 0.9038, a random effects model of 0.731, and a mixed effects model of only 0.473. Secondly, the

coefficients of the main variables in the three equations are very significant, and the import trade volume is inversely proportional to spatial distance and directly proportional to the total economic output, which is basically in line with the expected model settings and in line with the actual economic implications. Thirdly, the equation for mixed effects shows that China's preference for AFRICAN UNION (AU) member countries is 50% higher than that of non-AFRICAN UNION (AU) member countries and is significant at a 9% confidence level. Fourthly, based on the establishment of a random effects model, the Hausman adjoint probability value is 0.000, and the test results strongly reject the original hypothesis. Therefore, overall, fixed is more in line with the requirements of this article and better at solving the wooden text problem than random.

From the final regression results of the same effect model, it can be shown that controlling for other variables, for every 1% increase in the number of people in the trading country, China's imports to the trading country will increase by 1.6051%, while for every 1% increase in the number of people in the trading country, China's imports to the trading country will increase by 1.5672%.

Note: The main purpose of establishing the import model is to obtain the theoretical value of the import trade volume and prepare for the calculation of the import trade potential in the following text.

Table 2 Empirical results of the import trade gravity model between China and major trading partners

Variable	Effect Model A	Effect Model B	Effect Model C
GDP	0.64	1.57	1.63
Trade	0.12	1.61	0.185661
Distance	0.69		-0.59
African Union effect	0.50		0.87
North African Countries effect	0.18		-0.31
Adjusted R-Square	0.47	0.90	0.73
F-Statistics	68.20	137.08	204.91
Prob (F-Statistics)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hausman Test	N/A	N/A	0(2)

3.2 Empirical Testing of Trade Gravity Model

From the empirical results of 11 trade models between China and 30 countries (Table 3), it can be seen that: firstly, from the F-statistic and adjoint probability values of each model, it can be seen that: the regression equations are all significant, and the fitting degree of the three equations is improved compared to the import gravity model, and the adjusted R2 is above 69%, especially the explanatory degree of the fixed effects regression equation is as high as 94.89%. The coefficients of the main variables in the equation ($\ln Y, \ln Y_i, \ln \text{dist}$) are significant at a 99% confidence level. The export trade volume is inversely proportional to spatial distance and directly proportional to the total economic output, which basically meets the expectations set by the model and is also in line with the actual economic implications. Thirdly, both mixed effects and random effects set models show that the fitting coefficients of AFRICAN UNION (AU) variables have passed the significance test, indicating that AFRICAN UNION (AU) has effectively promoted the growth of China's export trade. Fourthly, the mixed effect regression equation shows that China's exports to NAF countries are 53.61% higher than those of non NAF countries, and are significant at a 99% confidence level. The mixed effects and random effects equations show that the sign of the Ad variable coefficient is the same as the expected sign, and it passes the significance test at a 95% confidence level, indicating that China is more inclined to export goods to neighboring countries in export trade. Fifthly, based on the establishment of a random effects model, the Hausman adjoint probability value is 0.000, and the 0 test results strongly reject the original hypothesis, that is, at a 99% confidence level,

fixed ratio randomness is more in line with the requirements of the wooden text and better solves the wooden text problem

From the final regression results of the fixed effects model, it can be shown that controlling for other variables, for every 1% increase in the population of trading countries, China's exports to trading countries will increase by 0.5531%, while for every 1% increase in the GDP of trading countries, China's exports to trading countries will increase by 1.8858

Note: The main purpose of establishing an export model is to obtain the theoretical value of export trade volume and prepare for the calculation of export trade potential in the following text

Table 3 Empirical results of the export trade gravity model between China and major trading partners

Variable	Effect Model A	Effect Model B	Effect Model C
GDP	0.99	1.89	1893965.00
Trade	-0.36	0.55	0.51
Distance	0.68		0.60
African Union effect	0.53		0.87
North African Countries effect	0.54		-0.187542
Adjusted R-Square	0.69	0.95	0.84
F-Statistics	168.64	270.02	400.60
Prob (F-Statistics)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hausman Test	N/A	N/A	0(2)

4. Calculation of Trade Potential Coefficient

4.1 Calculation method of trade potential coefficient

The import and export gravity model established above is a necessary tool for estimating the trade potential coefficient between China and one of the countries, and serves as a bridge for us to obtain specific import and export trade potential coefficients in the following text. The specific method for calculating the value of trade potential is: based on the gravity equation of import or export trade, a predicted value of export or import value is calculated, which is regarded as the theoretical value that the two countries should achieve in their natural state. The actual import and export trade value of the year is divided by its theoretical value, and the trade potential coefficient between China and the trading country can be calculated using this formula.

Import trade potential=actual import trade value of the current year/predicted import value estimated by gravity equation (theoretical value)

The actual value of export trade potential in the current year/the predicted export value estimated by the gravity equation (theoretical value)

4.2 Evaluation principles of trade potential coefficient

Generally speaking, the evaluation principle of trade potential is based on: if the trade potential coefficient between two countries is less than 1, it means that the two countries are in a state of "insufficient trade", which also indicates that the trade potential between the two countries is relatively large; On the contrary, if the trade potential coefficient between the two countries is high, it indicates that the trade between the two countries is in a "trade sufficient" state, indicating a lack of trade potential between the two countries; If the ratio is equal to 1, it indicates that the trade situation between the two countries is relatively ideal. From this, it can be roughly believed that the smaller the value of the trade potential coefficient between the two countries, the greater the trade potential between the two countries; On the contrary, if the value of the trade potential coefficient between two countries is larger, then the trade potential between the two countries is smaller. For how to define the numerical value of the potential coefficient, this article chooses to use one of the commonly used standards for studying trade potential in China and applying it to gravity models. For the

classification of specific measurement standards for trade potential, previous domestic research generally chose to use the method of Liu Jianfeng and Jiang Shuzhu (2007) to define bilateral trade potential:

(1) The potential is enormous, that is, when the ratio of actual bilateral trade volume to predicted bilateral trade volume is less than or equal to 80. According to the model analysis, there is a great potential for China to expand its trade scale with such trading partners. There are generally serious trade barriers between China and such trading partners, and the main idea for further development of trade relations is to quickly eliminate obstacles to trade development

(2) Potential development type, which refers to the situation where the ratio of actual bilateral trade volume to predicted bilateral trade volume is between 0.80 and 20. According to the model analysis, the potential for China to develop bilateral trade with this trading partner has not yet been fully realized, and there is still some room for expanding bilateral trade. The main idea for further developing trade relations with this trading partner is to learn from the approach of handling the first type of trade partnership, At the same time, pay attention to exploring the factors that contribute to the development of trade

(3) Potential reshaping refers to the situation where the ratio of actual bilateral trade volume to predicted bilateral trade volume is greater than or equal to. 20. The existing potential for China to expand trade scale with such trading partners has been exhausted according to model analysis. The main way to further develop trade relations with such trading partners is to maintain existing positive factors while developing and cultivating other factors that promote trade development.

5. Analysis Conclusion of Import and Export Trade Potential between China and North Africa

Based on the trade gravity model obtained after regression, the trade scale between China and 30 countries in 2022 was estimated to obtain the trade potential coefficients of these countries in 2022. Based on the above classification methods, two basic conclusions can be drawn as follows

Firstly, in China's import trade, the potential coefficients of import trade between China and the other four NAF countries are: China and Tunisia: 0.49 (with huge potential), China and Morocco: 0.57 (with huge potential), China and Algeria: 1.15 (with potential development), and China and Egypt: 2.81 (with potential reshaping)

Secondly, in China's export trade, the import potential coefficients between China and the other four NAF countries are: 0.67 (with huge potential) for China and Tunisia, 1.02 (with potential development) for China and Morocco, 1.16 (with potential development) for China and Egypt, and 1.17 (with potential development) for China and Algeria

Firstly, based on the import trade potential coefficient table, we can find that the import trade potential coefficient of China to Tunisia is 0.49, the import trade potential coefficient of China to Morocco is 0.57, the import trade potential coefficient of China to Algeria is 1.15, and the import trade potential coefficient of China to Egypt is as high as 2.81. The potential coefficient of China's import trade with Tunisia and Morocco is relatively low, ranking second and fifth in the import trade potential table, indicating a huge potential. This indicates that there may be significant trade barriers in China's import trade with Tunisia and Morocco, resulting in significant suppression of the development of trade between China

6. Conclusion

This article is based on previous scholars' research on the gravity model of trade, and based on the actual situation of China's import and export trade, attempts to establish a gravity model of China's impact on the import and export trade of the other four NAF countries, and use it to evaluate the potential of trade. Establishing a gravity model suitable for analyzing China's import and export trade potential with NAF countries

This article introduces new explanatory variables, such as the population of trading countries and virtual variables such as whether they are members of AFRICAN UNION (AU) or not. Considering that China often exhibits significant differences in imports and exports in its foreign trade, it is not scientific to only examine the total trade volume without distinguishing between imports and exports. Therefore, this article transforms the classic trade gravity model into two

gravity models: import and export trade. This article collected panel data from 30 countries for a total of 19 years from 2004 to 2022, with a total of 570 valid samples. From the final regression results of the fixed effects model, it is shown that for every 1% increase in the population of other variables, China's imports to trading countries will increase by 1.6051%, while for every 1% increase in the GD of trading countries, China's imports to trading countries will increase by 1.5672%.

In the table of China's potential for NAF countries, China and Morocco belong to the category of huge potential, while China and Tunisia belong to the category of huge potential; China and Cuba belong to the category of potential development; China and Egypt belong to potential reshaping. In the table of export potential of NAF countries, China and Tunisia belong to the category of huge potential; China and Morocco belong to the category of potential development; China and Egypt belong to the category of potential development; China and Cuba belong to the category of potential development. From this, it can be seen that in addition to China's fully utilized import trade potential with Egypt, there is room for China's import and export trade with these four countries to further stimulate their trade potential.

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